

SHORT NOTES

Synthesis of Alkoxy-Siloxy Derivatives of Tantalum

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Bradley and Thomas¹ reported the synthesis of trialkylaloxo derivatives of tantalum by the reactions of tantalum pentaethoxide with trialkylsilanol², or trialkylsilylacetate³ and by the reaction of tantalum dialkylamide with triethyl silanol⁴. Recently, a number of mixed alkoxy-siloxy derivatives of aluminium⁵, titanium⁶ and tin⁷ have been reported. In view of the above, it was considered of interest to synthesise the mixed ethoxy-siloxy derivatives of tantalum by the reaction of tantalum pentaethoxide and trimethyl acetoxy silane.

During the course of the present study, the tantalum pentaethoxide was taken in cyclohexane and to it was added, trimethyl acetoxy silane in cyclohexane dropwise in different stoichiometric ratios. The contents were refluxed for 2-4 hours with continuous slow fractionation. Excess solvent was distilled, and product was dried under reduced pressure. The results of various reactions may be represented as follows:

All these products are colourless viscous pastes and disproportionate on heating under reduced pressure. The addition of trimethyl acetoxy silane in cyclohexane was done slowly to tantalum pentaethoxide because the trimethyl acetoxy silane appears to acetylate the siloxy-tantalum compound.

EXPERIMENTAL

Experimental techniques and reagents were similar to those described previously⁸.

1. Bradley, and Thomas, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1959 3404.
2. Bradley and Thomas: *Chem. and Ind.*, 1958 17.
3. Bradley and Thomas, *Chem. and Ind.*, 1958 1231.
4. Thomas, *Can. J. Chem.*, 1961 39, 1385.
5. Mehrotra and Pant, *Ind. J. Appl. Chem.*, 1963 26 109.
6. Nakaido, *Kogyo Kagaku Zasshi*, 1964 67, 236.
7. Mehrotra and Gupta, *Ind. J. Chem.* (Communicated).
8. Mehrotra and Kapoor, *J. Less-Common Metals*, 1964, 7, 453.

Trimethyl chlorosilane and acetic anhydride was distilled before use. Trimethyl acetoxy silane was prepared by the reaction between trimethyl chlorosilane and acetic anhydride. The acetyl chloride formed was removed continuously and thus a higher yield of acetoxy silane was obtained.

Tantalum was estimated as tantalum pentoxide. The sample was weighed in a platinum crucible and dissolved in the ethanol. Ammonia was added and the mixture, cautiously evaporated to dryness by using an infra-red lamp. It was fully ignited and weighed as the oxide. Ethoxide was determined by the chromic acid method⁹ which was found to be unaffected by the presence of the trimethyl siloxy group.

Reaction between tantalum pentaethoxide and trimethyl acetoxy-silane Molar ratio 1:1: Tantalum pentaethoxide (2.73 g) was weighed in two necked flask, and 30 ml of dry cyclohexane added. To one of the necks was fitted a fractionating column and to the other a dropping funnel containing trimethyl acetoxy silane (0.89 g) in cyclohexane (30 ml). The contents were allowed to reflux at a bath temperature of 110° in such a manner that the solvent vapour reached up to the top. The solution from the funnel was now added dropwise and cyclohexane-ethylacetate azeotrope began to be collected from the top at 71-73°. When the addition was completed (3 hours), the whole solution was refluxed further for 2 hours and distillate was collected at the top. The residue was dried at 30°/0.5 mm whereby a white viscous liquid (2.98 g) was obtained. Found: Ta, 40.26; ethoxy, 38.3%. Calc. for Ta(OEt)₅(OSiMe₃)₂; Ta, 41.1; ethoxy, 40.9%.

For brevity, results of reactions in other molar ratios are summarised in Table I.

TABLE I

Reactions between Tantalum pentaethoxide and trimethylacetoxy silane in cyclohexane

S. No.	Reactants in (g)		Molar ratio	Products and Nature	Analysis%			
	A	B			Ta		Ethoxy	
				Found	Calc.	Found	Calc.	
1.	A	3.32	1:2	Ta (OEt) ₅ (OSiMe ₃) ₂ * White viscous liquid (3.92)	97.70	36.60	27.43	27.90
	B	2.16						
2.	A	3.70	1:3	Ta (OEt) ₅ (OSiMe ₃) ₃ White viscous paste (4.89)	34.92	33.60	16.38	16.70
	B	3.60						
3.	A	2.78	1:4	Ta (OEt) ₅ (OSiMe ₃) ₄ White viscous paste (4.10)	32.42	31.10	7.46	7.70
	B	3.62						

Where A=Tantalum pentaethoxide; B=Trimethylacetoxy silane

*Disproportionates on heating.

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Measurement of Copper, Zinc, Manganese, Cobalt, Nickel Ion Activities in Aqueous Solutions by Membrane Electrodes and Determination of their Mobility Ratio

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Clay membrane electrodes have been successfully utilised for the determination of ion activities of NH_4^+ , K^+ , Na^+ , Mg^{++} , Ca^{++} , Ba^{++} . For this purpose Padegaon Ca-form and aquagel Ca-form membranes are found to be the best. Mitra and Chatterjee have extended the use of clay membrane electrode to measurements of ion activity of copper¹, zinc, manganese and cobalt². In this communication, an attempt has been made to ascertain if some of the clay membrane electrodes used in this investigation³ could be utilised for measuring Cu, Zn, Mn, Co, Ni ion activities in solution and also to evaluate mobility ratios of selected ion pairs.

EXPERIMENTAL

The experimental set-up was similar to that mentioned earlier⁴. Results on the measurements of copper, zinc, manganese, cobalt, nickel ion activities are reported in the Table I. The calculated mobility ratios of the pairs, UZn/UCu , UMn/UCu , UMn/UZn , UCo/UNi , UMn/UNi , UMn/UCo are given in Table II.

DISCUSSION

The results show that the range of activity over which the Nernst equation is valid, depends, besides the nature of the cation whose activity is measured, on the nature of the cation originally saturating the membrane and the nature of the minerals constituting the membrane. Thus, it is observed that 0.5 μ size Padegaon Ca-form membrane performs well of the lot in the measurement of Mn^{++} in solution. Using this membrane, the satisfactory range of cation activity measurement is between 0.0001 and 0.0081 for copper, manganese, cobalt, nickel and between 0.0001 and 0.0243 for zinc. Similar observations were made earlier by Mitra and Chatterjee¹.

Of the pairs studied, the mobility ratio is greatest with Mn/Cu and least with Co/Ni. The order is UCo/UNi , UMn/UZn , UMn/UCo , UMn/UNi , UZn/UCu , UMn/UCu . The differences in the standard potentials of the pairs of elements in aqueous solutions⁵, are as follows: $E^\circ\text{Co}-E^\circ\text{Ni}=0.04$ volt, $E^\circ\text{Mn}-E^\circ\text{Zn}=0.24$ volt, $E^\circ\text{Mn}-E^\circ\text{Co}=0.78$ volt, $E^\circ\text{Mn}-E^\circ\text{Ni}=0.82$ volt, $E^\circ\text{Zn}-E^\circ\text{Cu}=1.10$ volt, $E^\circ\text{Mn}-E^\circ\text{Cu}=1.39$ volt.

1. Mitra and Chatterjee, *J. Indian Soc. Soil Sci.*, 1953, 1, 12.
2. *Idem*, *J. Ind. Chem. Soc.*, 1955, 32, 751.
3. Adhikari, *J. Ind. Chem. Soc.*, 1961, 38, 817.
4. *Idem*, *ibid.*, 1963, 40, 569, 985.
5. Conway - Electrochemical data, Elsevier Pub., 1952.

This is also the order of the mobility ratios, as has been indicated above. It was suggested by Mitra⁶ and Bose⁷ that if the clay membrane is supposed to act in a manner similar to a metal-metal ion electrode within the validity of the Nernst equation, the mobility ratio may be related to E° values for the cation pair concerned, *e.g.*, for the pair, $\text{Co}^{2+}-\text{Ni}^{2+}$, $E^{\circ}\text{Ni}$, $\text{Co}=\text{RT}/2F \ln U_{\text{Co}}/U_{\text{Ni}}$. The agreement in the sequence of the differences of e.m.f. values lends some support to the contention of Mitra and Bose, but a quantitative agreement is not to be expected because other parameters in the electrode reaction which are likely to be involved remain unknown.

TABLE I
Ion activity measurements
(mean values of observed e.m.f. in m.v.), Temp. 25°.

Membrane	(a) Activity of Cu^{2+} ion				
Inside soln. activity	0.0001	0.0003	0.0009	0.0081	0.0081
Outside soln. activity	0.0003	0.0009	0.0027	0.0027	0.243
Padegaon 0.5 μ size					
Ca-form	14.2	14.1	14.2	14.2	12.0
Na-form	14.2	14.2	14.1	14.3	11.0
Aquagel, Ca-form	14.2	14.2	14.1	14.3	6.4
Theoretical value of e.m.f.	14.1	14.1	14.1	14.1	14.1
(b) Activity of Mn^{2+} ion					
Padegaon 0.5 μ size					
Ca-form	14.2	14.1	14.2	14.2	11.0
Na-form	14.2	14.3	14.2	13.6	6.4
Aquagel, Ca-form	14.2	14.3	14.3	13.8	3.4
Theoretical value of e.m.f.	14.1	14.1	14.1	14.1	14.1
(c) Activity of Ni^{2+} ion					
Padegaon, 0.5 μ size					
Ca-form	14.1	14.1	14.2	14.1	12.4
Na-form	14.1	14.2	14.3	14.2	8.5
Aquagel, Ca-form	14.1	14.3	14.3	14.3	7.6
Theoretical value of e.m.f.	14.1	14.1	14.1	14.1	14.1
(d) Activity of Co^{2+} ion					
Padegaon, 0.5 μ size					
Ca-form	14.2	14.2	14.2	14.1	13.0
Na-form	14.2	14.2	14.2	14.0	11.7
Aquagel, Ca-form	14.2	14.3	14.3	13.8	7.6
Theoretical value of e.m.f.	14.1	14.1	14.1	14.1	14.1
(e) Activity of Zn^{2+} ion					
Padegaon, 0.5 μ size					
Ca-form	14.2	14.1	14.2	14.2	14.2
Na-form	14.2	14.1	14.0	14.0	13.6
Aquagel, Ca-form	14.2	14.1	14.3	13.8	12.7
Theoretical value of e.m.f.	14.1	14.1	14.1	14.1	14.1

6. Mitra, D. Phil. Thesis, Calcutta University, 1954.

7. Bose, *J. Indian Soc. Soil Sci.*, 1955, 3, 109.

TABLE II

*Mobility ratio measurements*Membrane used: Padegaon, 0.5 μ size, Ca-form, Temp. 25°.

Mean value observed e.m.f. in m.v.

Inside solution forms the (—) ve part of the cell.

<u>Inside soln. activity</u>	0.0003 Mn ²⁺	0.0003 Zn ²⁺	0.0003 Mn ²⁺		0.0003 Zn ²⁺
<u>Outside soln. activity</u>	0.0003 Cu ²⁺	0.0003 Cu ²⁺			0.0003 Zn ²⁺
Obs. e.m.f.	53.0	Obs. e.m.f.	42.0	Obs. e.m.f.	11.5
UMn/UCu	7.9	Uzn/UCu	5.15	UMn/UZn	1.57
<u>Inside soln. activity</u>	0.0003 Co ²⁺	0.0003 Mn ²⁺		0.0003 Mn ²⁺	
<u>Outside soln. activity</u>	0.0003 Ni ²⁺	0.0003 Ni ²⁺		0.0003 Co ²⁺	
Obs. e.m.f.	6.4	Obs. e.m.f.	36.0	Obs. e.m.f.	30.5
UCo/UNi	1.28	UMn/UNi	4.10	UMn/UCo	3.28

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